

A METHOD OF QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS WITHOUT THE USE OF HYDROGEN SULPHIDE.

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The obvious undesirability of the obnoxious and poisonous hydrogen sulphide gas as a necessary reagent in the chemical laboratory, induced many previous workers to devise alternative schemes of qualitative analysis avoiding its use. Fresenius ("Qualitative Analysis", 17th Ed, translated by Mitchell, pp. 836-849), gives the details of five such alternative methods, *viz:*—

- (i) Schiff and Tarugi's thioacetate method
- (ii) Vortmann's sodium sulphide method
- (iii) Votmann's thiosulphate method
- (iv) Ebler and Knoevenagel's method of separation by means of hydrazine and hydroxylamine salts
- (v) Alinkvist's method using potassium hydroxide and potassium carbonate.

In these methods, however, sulphides of alkalis and other thio-salts, not less undesirable, are freely used. It was only recently that a method in which hydrogen sulphide in any form is specifically eschewed, has been worked out by O. Macchia (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 27, 180). The method, however, is rather complicated and elaborate.

The present method, in which the bases are divided into five groups, gives a sharp and satisfactory separation and is expeditious. No special modification is needed even in presence of phosphates, oxalates, etc. The method has been verified in the laboratory by analysing a number of complex mixtures containing 10 or 12 bases and the results have been quite satisfactory. The scheme confined to the common base is outlined in Table I.

TABLE I.

Separation of the basic constituents into groups.

Treat the mixture with hydrochloric acid and evaporate with nitric acid : take up with nitric acid and filter.				
Residue :—	Filtrate +	ammonium sulphate.		
Ag, Sb, Sn and Insoluble matter	Ppt. :— Ba, Sr, Pb, (Ca)	Filtrate :—Test for phosphoric acid. Add ammonia and ammonium phosphate		
	Ppt. —	Filtrate :—Heat with NaOH		
	Na, Al, Cr			
	Mn, Bi,	Ppt. :—	Filtrate :	
	Ca, Mg	Co, Ni,	Zn & As—	
	(As)	Cu, Cd Hg		
Group I.	Group II.	Group III.	Group IV.	Group V.

About 1 g. of the mixture is treated in a Casserole with 5-10 c.c. of 12*N*-hydrochloric acid, heated and then without filtering, boiled with 10 c.c. of 16*N*-nitric acid, evaporated to dryness, the residue treated with 5 c.c. more of the acid, warmed and filtered (*cf.* Note 1). The residue is washed with 6 *N*-nitric acid and treated as Group I. The filtrate is treated with 15-20 c.c. of a 20% ammonium sulphate solution, heated to boiling, allowed to stand a little, and filtered. The precipitate contains Ba, Sr (Ca) and Pb as sulphates. About 2 c.c. of the filtrate from above is tested separately in cold, with ammonium molybdate for the presence of phosphate (*cf.* Note 2).

Note 1. Experiments have shown that Sb_2O_5 , formed under the circumstances, is practically insoluble in nitric acid 6*N* and above, though slightly soluble in acid of lesser concentrations (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 544).

Note 2. In presence of ammonium sulphate, the phosphomolybdate precipitate is thrown down readily in cold (distinction from arsenomolybdate which requires boiling for precipitation,

The rest of the solution is heated to boiling and a liberal excess of 6*N*-ammonia is added until a strong smell persists, and then a hot solution of 1*N*-ammonium phosphate until there is no further precipitation (*cf.* Note 3). The precipitate is treated as Group III (*cf.* Note 4).

The filtrate from the above is boiled with 15-20 c.c. of a 3*N*-sodium hydroxide solution. The precipitate is washed with NaOH solution and treated as Group IV. Zn and As, forming Group V, are tested for in the filtrate from Group IV, while the alkalis are tested for in the original mixture.

GROUP I

Residue from hydrochloric and nitric acid treatment: Treat with 6*N* ammonium hydroxide, filter and wash.

Residue :—Stannic oxide, antimony pentoxide and other acid insoluble matter. Treat with ammonium acetate and filter. Filtrate :—Acidify with 6*N*-nitric acid. White ppt.

Residue :—Digest with 5-10 c.c. of 12 *N*-hydrochloric acid and filter. Filtrate :—Test for lead with chromate. Ag.

Residue :—Acid insol. matter. Treat in the usual way. Filtrate :—Chlorides of tin and antimony. Heat with reduced iron powder and filter.

Residue :—Black metallic antimony. Dissolve and confirm as usual. Filtrate :—Stannous chloride. Confirm by HgCl_2 test.

GROUP II.

Treat the precipitate with 5—15 c.c. of 3*N*-ammonium acetate and filter.

Residue :—Boil with 25 c.c. of saturated sodium carbonate solution, with a pinch of the solid (Na_2CO_3). Decant through a filter and repeat the process. Filtrate :—Test with potassium chromate. Yellow ppt. soluble in sodium hydroxide, Pb.

Residue : Carbonates of Ba, Sr, Ca and Pb if any. Take up with nitric acid and remove lead by addition of NH_4OH and test the filtrate for alkaline earths as usual. Filtrate :— Na_2SO_4 reject.

Note 3. Ammonium phosphate is added to precipitate here Ca, Mg. and Mn also.

Note 4. Ordinarily mercury is precipitated with ammonia and ammonium phosphate ; the presence of excess of ammonium sulphate, however, keeps it in solution.

GROUP III.

Precipitate : Hydroxides, phosphates or arsenates of Fe, Al, Cr, Bi, Mn, Ca and Mg.

Dissolve in 6N-hydrochloric acid, and treat with sodium carbonate and sodium peroxide and filter.

Ppt. :—Fe, Mn, Bi, Ca and Mg. Dissolve in 6N-nitric acid, with a little H_2O_2 if necessary; evaporate, and boil with 6N-nitric acid and potassium chlorate.

Filtrate :—Aluminate, chromate, phosphate, arsenate of sodium. Acidify with hydrochloric acid, test one portion for As, after reduction with SO_2 , by Bettendorf test and add ammonia to the rest.

Ppt. :—Black MnO_2 ; confirm as usual.

Filtrate :—Add ammonium chloride and ammonia.

Ppt. :—Bi & Fe. Dissolve in HCl and add granulated zinc, heat and filter.

Filtrate :—Ca, Mg. Separate test as usual

Ppt. :—Dissolve in sodium hydroxide and treat with barium chloride and filter.

Filtrate :—Yellow, chromate Cr. Confirm as usual.

Residue : Black Bi; dissolve in nitric acid and confirm by alkaline stannite test.

Filtrate Fe. Oxidise, and confirm as usual.

Ppt.—Barium phosphate, reject.

Filtrate :—Al. Acidify and test as usual.

To the solution of Group III precipitate in 6N-hydrochloric acid, which should be about 25 c.c. in volume, a saturated solution of sodium carbonate is added to turbidity. It is then cooled and a little sodium peroxide powder and 1-2 g. of sodium carbonate added and the mixture boiled slowly for about 10 minutes. It is diluted with 10 c.c. of water, and filtered by decantation; the residue is treated again with a few c.c. of hydrochloric acid, neutralised and boiled with about 1 g. of sodium carbonate for 5 minutes and finally filtered and washed. The precipitate contains Fe, Bi, Mn, Ca and Mg as hydroxides or carbonates. (*Cf. note 5*).

Note 5. The treatment with sodium carbonate and sodium peroxide was found to convert practically completely the oxalates and phosphates of this group into carbonates.

GROUP IV.

Ppt.:—Oxides or phosphates of Ni, Co, Cu, Cd and Hg. Dissolve in 6*N*-hydrochloric acid and treat with Al and filter (*cf.* Note 6).

Ppt.:—Cu and Hg in metallic condition. Filtrate:—Treat with sodium hydroxide solution in excess, filter and wash.

Test a small portion of ppt. with Cu foil for Hg.	Dissolve bulk of ppt. in nitric acid; boil off excess acid and test for Cu with potassium ferrocyanide in the usual way.	Ppt.:—Cd, Co, Ni. Dissolve in acetic acid and treat with ammonium oxalate, filter and wash.	Filtrate:—Al. Reject
		Ppt.:—White Cd oxalate; dissolve in as little HCl as possible and add potassium ferricyanide, yellow ppt. Cd.	Filtrate:—Co, Ni. Concentrate and test, for Co with KNO_2 and for Ni, with dimethyl glyoxime in the usual way.

GROUP V.

Solution:—Zn and As.

Acidify with hydrochloric acid and boil with 3*N*-sodium carbonate solution and filter.

Ppte.:—Zn CO_3 . Dissolve in HCl and confirm by ferrocyanide test or Rinmann's green test with the Zn CO_3 . Filtrate:—Sodium arsenate. Reduce with SO_2 and test for As by Bettendorff test.

GROUP VI.

(NH_4), K and Na.

The original mixture is treated with water containing a few c.c. of 6*N* HCl and filtered. A small portion of the filtrate is tested for (NH_4) by sodium hydroxide and the Na and K are tested for in the bulk of the solution, after removing other bases by Ba (OH)₂ and H₂SO₄ treatment, in the usual way.

Note 6. Treatment of the hydrochloric acid solution of Group IV ppt. with a small piece of Al foil precipitates all the Cu and Hg. Some nickel and cobalt may also be precipitated here. After the Al piece goes in solution, add about 5 c.c. of 6*N*-HCl and allow to stand a little when, precipitated Ni & Co, if any, would go in solution.